

Reproduce Paper "Answering Count Queries with Explanatory Evidence"

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Assignment Two: Group 28-A

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This paper represents a different approach to count queries such as "number of songs by John Lennon" instead of representing just a number of songs and not other factual information with this approach it is intended to get a more precise answer by gathering information from several sources, this system derives answers from multiple sources, incorporates semantic qualifiers to refine counts, and supports its conclusions by listing representative examples. Authors also have made available a dataset containing 5,000 queries and 200,000 relevant text snippets.

1 Introduction

In the past 10 years a significant change has been made in question answering and online search using the telegraphic questions. Still there are queries that have multiple correct answers due to variance in semantic qualifiers that are an interesting field for research. In this paper that we are trying to reproduce the topic of count queries is addressed. Examples of these queries can be "How many songs did John Lennon write for the Beatles?" as seen in paper. If the count queries data is in a structured way as in knowledge base than the answer is straightforward and returned. Search engines handle popular cases well but they have issues when the question is more detailed like in the example above "for the Beatles" which is a subset of all John Lennon songs. Answering these count queries poses some challenges like: Aggregation and inference, Contextualization, Explanatory Evidence.

In this paper there is a different approach to these kind of queries that is presented called CoQEx, "Count Question answering with Explanatory evidence" which answers these queries by the help of three components answer inference, answer contextualization and answer explanation. [1]

For answering a query "CoQEx applies joint inference to compute a highconfidence answer for the count itself." [1]

Contribution of these paper:

- introducing the problem of count query answering with explanatory evidence.
- developing a method for inferring high-confidence counts from noisy candidate sets.
- developing techniques to provide answer contextualization and explanations;
- releasing an annotated data resource with 5k count queries and 200k text passages, with preliminary access for reviewing at <https://github.com/ghoshs/CoQEx>
- evaluating CoQEx against state-of-the-art baselines on a variety of test queries;

2 Related Work

There are some related work and approaches that work with the issue of count queries and below there are shown some of them. Structured data in Knowledge Bases have structure data that can be used to answer queries such as the count queries but these data can be incomplete when it is needed more details to them or a more specific count query such as "number of songs by John Lennon".

Recent researches also explored QA over web tables, with focus on table retrieval and span prediction [2]. Another challenge is connecting the gap of natural language queries and the formulation of queries in systems like SPARQL. Reducing this gap could improve count query answering. State of the art QA most of the time use machine reading approach where it finds the answer inside a text. This involves checking text segments to find the best answer or ranked documents list. QA systems sometimes incomplete information or incorrect ones.

Another attempt or research field is hybrid QA on the text and KB but yet with no specific consideration on the count queries.[4, 6]. It is recognized that just literally answering questions is often not sufficient for use cases. In the next chapter it is more detailed on the methodology used for answering count queries.

Figure 1: System overview of CoQEx.

3 Methodology

The authors had the approach of answering the count queries by combining the per-document answer span prediction, context extraction, and consolidation of counts and instances across documents. In Fig 1 an overview of the approach can be seen (CoQEx). It was getting the answer for questions like this "How many songs did John Lennon write for the Beatles" where a count questions has a relation with another subject in this case "for the Beatles" and its a bit more complicated to answer. It assumes that relevant document (information) or passages are given. The focus is on identifying and counting specific entities mentioned in the text. The process goes in to three stages: consolidate the counts to present the best answer, present contextualization as a means to semantically qualifying the predicted count, and ground the count in instances.

3.1 Answer Inference For getting the answer candidates for the count queries researchers used SpanBERT model [3] trained on the e CoQuAD train split for candidate generation. Model predictions return general text spans, which these answers have two components the count itself and qualifiers, which we separate with the help of the CogComp Quantifier [5]. To consolidate the resulting candidates counts four methods are compared: Most confident, Most frequent, Median, Weighted Median.

3.2 Answer Contextualization Candidates given from the Answer Inference usually contains nouns with phrasal modifiers. The research call them count-modified noun phrases(CNPs).In answer inference, the most accurate count-modified noun phrase (CNP) is chosen as the representative (CNPrep) based on its count be-

ing closest to the predicted count. The CNP selected is the one with the highest confidence within this range. The remaining CNP are categorized as follows: Subgroups, Synonyms and Incomparables more for there can be read in the paper on how the selection of this groups is made.

3.3 Answer Explanation In the last step after classifying count answer contexts, showing relevant sample instances in paper another step is explain-ability, the aim is to identify entities that are among the ones counted in the query. Also here the researches used the SpanBERT model to obtain candidates but with a slightly different questions from "how many" to "which" or adding "which in the question" and then rank the answers spans by using these approaches: QA w/o Consolidation, QA + Context Frequency, QA + Summed Confidence, QA + Type Compatibility more detail in these approaches can be found on the paper.

4 Dataset

For this solution, two datasets were provided: one for training and another for testing purposes. The training dataset comprises over 4,000 queries, while the test dataset is somewhat smaller, containing around 500 queries. Each dataset is structured, featuring queries alongside metadata such as the number of organic search results, snippet counts, and a normalized answer metric, among others. Moreover, the dataset has a variety of topics, with a significant focus on entertainment (27%), followed by social issues (20%), organizations (12%), technology (8%), and politics (7%). Analysis reveals that 20% of the queries provide completely stable results, such as the founders of a company or movie casts, while 55% have low volatility, including topics like regional lakes or members of a well-known but currently active band. The remaining 25% are subject to frequent updates, covering areas like employment statistics or COVID-19 case numbers.

4.1 Training dataset: The training dataset consists of 9 columns which include qid (query ID), query (the text of the query), num_organic_results (number of organic search results), num_count_spans, num_neg_snip, num_snip (related to snippets, indicating the count of snippets, negative snippets, and total snippets respectively), answer_relation, answer_norm (normalized answer value), and answer_metric (this column is present but empty in the dataset). The training dataset contains mixes integers, floating-point numbers, and text data, indicating a combination of numerical, categorical, and textual information.

4.2 Test dataset: The test dataset shares the same structure as the training dataset, ensuring consistency in evaluation. Similar to the training set, it has a variety in `num_snip` and `answer_norm` values, even though on a smaller scale due to the reduced size of the dataset.

5 Reproduction

In our attempt to replicate the study’s findings, we initiated the process with the open-source GitHub repository, which served as a solid starting point and provided a clear roadmap for the tasks at hand. Our primary objective was to locally host the application, anticipating a smooth execution to determine the feasibility of adding extra data—a critical aspect we aimed to explore for enhancing dataset accuracy.

The first challenge were the modules, which were configured for specific users running the application, which required us to rename along with all other parts of the application to ensure the functionality of the Flask application server.

The script for downloading the dataset, fetching both the train and evaluation data of CoQuAD, proceeded smoothly. We obtained the latest dataset using the provided shell script, fetching and unzipping files from a Nextcloud instance.

Subsequently, we encountered references to CoQEx-hosted models that were no longer available in the project’s references. So, we realigned with Hugging Face, establishing paths for models such as SpanBERT and Facebook AI Roberta Large.

Progress appeared promising until an unexpected roadblock arose with the ‘static data’ folder. We were unable to find any information or documentation on its generation, thereby not allowing us the execution of the final step of the process—counting the results of the model responses.

In summary, our approach to replicate the study’s results was a blend of untangling complexities and overcoming unforeseen challenges.

6 Results and Analysis

In an evaluation of the CoQEx question-answering system, the analysis reveals that CoQEx outperforms other systems like SpanBERT and GoogleSDA in terms of coverage and precision. CoQEx’s implementation utilizes transformer-based models, fine-tuned for answering inference tasks. The Context Precision (CP) is used to assess the accuracy of answer count predictions. The system demonstrates su-

perior performance, particularly when employing weighted median consolidation techniques, which significantly improve answer inference by considering the variance in data. The system’s approach to handling Compound Noun Phrases (CNPs) achieves high accuracy, especially for synonyms by maintaining a threshold for variation acceptance.

The CoQEx provides more accurate and structured responses, showing the benefits of structured knowledge bases for enhancing answer quality. User studies involving MTurk participants favor interfaces that combine bare counts, instances, and CNPs, suggesting a preference for detailed and explanatory answer pages. The effectiveness is quantitatively supported by metrics such as Precision at k ($P@k$), Recall at k ($R@k$), Hit@10, and Mean Reciprocal Rank (MRR) across various datasets, which highlight CoQEx’s robustness and the added value of its explanation components.

7 Discussion And Conclusion

The paper presents an innovative approach to answering count queries with explanatory evidence, called CoQEx. This method significantly improves upon traditional count query answers by incorporating semantic qualifiers and presenting detailed, evidence-backed answers drawn from multiple sources. Through the methodology, the effectiveness of the system in delivering more accurate and contextually rich responses compared to current state-of-the-art systems is demonstrated. The evaluation shows its superior performance over existing approaches, emphasizing the importance of detailed, evidence-based responses in query answering systems. Despite efforts to replicate the study’s findings, challenges such as module configurations and unavailable referenced models were encountered, highlighting the complexities of practical application.

References

- [1] Shrestha Ghosh, Simon Razniewski, and Gerhard Weikum. Answering count queries with explanatory evidence. In *Proceedings of the 45th International ACM SIGIR Conference on Research and Development in Information Retrieval*, SIGIR ’22. ACM, Jul 2022.
- [2] Jonathan Herzig, Thomas Müller, Syrine Krichene, and Julian Eisenschlos. Open domain question answering over tables via dense retrieval. In Kristina Toutanova, Anna Rumshisky, Luke Zettlemoyer, Dilek Hakkani-Tur, Iz Beltagy, Steven Bethard, Ryan Cotterell, Tanmoy Chakraborty, and Yichao Zhou,

editors, *Proceedings of the 2021 Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Human Language Technologies*, pages 512–519, Online, June 2021. Association for Computational Linguistics.

- [3] Mandar Joshi, Danqi Chen, Yinhan Liu, Daniel S. Weld, Luke Zettlemoyer, and Omer Levy. SpanBERT: Improving pre-training by representing and predicting spans. *Transactions of the Association for Computational Linguistics*, 8:64–77, 2020.
- [4] Xiaolu Lu, Soumajit Pramanik, Rishiraj Saha Roy, Abdalghani Abujabal, Yafang Wang, and Gerhard Weikum. Answering complex questions by joining multi-document evidence with quasi knowledge graphs. *CoRR*, abs/1908.00469, 2019.
- [5] Subhro Roy, Tim Vieira, and Dan Roth. Reasoning about Quantities in Natural Language. *Transactions of the Association for Computational Linguistics*, 3:1–13, 01 2015.
- [6] Kun Xu, Yansong Feng, Songfang Huang, and Dongyan Zhao. Hybrid question answering over knowledge base and free text. In Yuji Matsumoto and Rashmi Prasad, editors, *Proceedings of COLING 2016, the 26th International Conference on Computational Linguistics: Technical Papers*, pages 2397–2407, Osaka, Japan, December 2016. The COLING 2016 Organizing Committee.